

A Synthesis of Chroman-3-One

J. N. Chatterjea, B. K. Banerjee and K. Achari

A convenient synthesis of chroman-3-one has been described and the chemistry of the compound studied.

Chroman-3-one and its derivatives have been prepared by the cyclisation of *o*-carboxy-methoxyphenylacetic acids (acetic anhydride-sodium acetate or Dieckmann cyclisation of the ester)^{1,2,3}. A different synthesis has been described by Sheffer and Moore⁴ by the acid catalysed decomposition of 1-diazo-3(*o*-anisyl)-2-propanone. A convenient preparation of the chroman-3-one and its derivatives is now reported from chromene-3-carboxylic acid (I) which was converted by standard procedures into the urethane (III) by way of the azide (II). The urethane on boiling with dilute sulphuric acid gave chroman-3-one (56%). In a similar manner, 6-methylchroman-3-one was obtained (42%) from (IV). An authentic sample of the latter ketone was secured by the boron trifluoride catalysed cyclisation of the diazoketone derived from 3-methyl-6-methoxyphenylacetic acid following Sheffer and Moore⁴.

The chromanones showed i.r. absorption at 1720 cm^{-1} and was characterised by the preparation of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and 3:5-dinitrobenzoate. Chroman-3-one polymerised on keeping and the 6-methyl derivative behaved similarly. An aged specimen of the former deposited the self-condensation product (V), m.p. 131–34° (i.r. absorption 3420 and 1718 cm^{-1}) which appears to be different from a compound m.p. 172.5–174.5° described by Pfeiffer and Bauer⁵ who obtained it by the action of sodium hydroxide on 4-ethoxycarbonylchroman-3-one.

1. P. Pfeiffer and E. Enders, *Ber.*, 1951, **84**, 247.
2. James H. Richards, A. Robertson and J. Ward., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1610.
3. Masateru Miyano, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 3958.
4. Howard E. Sheffer and James A. Moore, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 129.
5. P. Pfeiffer and K. Bauer, *Ber.*, 1947, **80**, 7.

Chroman-3-one underwent an exothermic Fischer indole reaction giving (VI, R = H) and a similar product (VI, R = CH₃) was obtained from 6-methylchroman-3-one. The reaction with Grignard's reagent is complicated by the fact that most of the enolic magnesium salt is thrown down during the reaction. However, with phenylmagnesium bromide and chroman-3-one the related carbinol was isolated (yield, 45%) which afforded the isoflavilium salt (VII) on treatment with triphenylmethylperchlorate. This, therefore, opens up a different route to isoflavilium salts which have been recently prepared by others^{6,7}.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Chroman-3-one : Chromene-3-carboxylic acid (9.0 g.) prepared by the method of Taylor and Tomlinson⁸ was refluxed with thionyl chloride (15.0 ml.) for 2 hr. on waterbath. The excess of the thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure and the last traces removed by the addition of dry benzene followed by removal under vacuum. The residual *acid chloride* was a thick oil of deep brown colour. This was dissolved in dry acetone (50 ml.) at 0° and treated with a solution of sodium azide (6.0 g.) in water (25 ml.) dropwise. After stirring for 10 minutes, cold water was added when the azide, m.p. 60° (gas evolution) separated. It was collected and dried in vacuum desiccator.

The azide (8.5 g.) was refluxed with absolute ethanol (50 ml.) for 1.5 hours, when the solid dissolved after brisk evolution of nitrogen. Alcohol was then removed under vacuum when the urethane was obtained as thick oil. It was then refluxed with sulphuric acid (50 ml.; 10%) for 3.5 hours, cooled and extracted with ether. On removal of the solvent, *chroman-3-one* distilled at 80°/1 mm. as a colourless oil.

The 2 : 4-*dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from acetic acid in dull red needles, m.p. 165° (decomp.). (Lit.¹, m.p. 165–66°).

The *semicarbazone* prepared in the usual manner was crystallised from alcohol as white needles, m.p. 187–88° (Lit.¹, m.p. 188.5°). (Found : C, 59.29; H, 6.1. Calc. for C₁₀H₁₁O₂N₃ : C, 58.53; H, 5.4%).

The 3 : 5-*dinitrobenzoate* was prepared in pyridine and crystallised from acetic acid as golden yellow needles, m.p. 201–02°. (Found : C, 56.02; H, 3.7. C₁₆H₁₀O₇N₂ requires C, 56.14; H, 2.9%).

Self-condensation of chroman-3-one : The chroman-3-one (0.1 g.) on long standing (ca. 8 months) furnished a crystalline product. It was triturated with a little alcohol, filtered and crystallised from alcohol when the self-condensation product (V) separated as hard crystals, m.p. 131–34°. On further crystallisation, the melting point did not change. (Found : C, 72.3; H, 5.33. C₁₈H₁₆O₄ requires C, 72.9; H, 5.4%). The IR spectrum showed absorption at 3420 cm⁻¹ (hydroxyl) and 1718 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ketone).

The 2 : 4-*dinitrophenylhydrazone* was crystallised from ethyl acetate as orange needles, m.p. 177–78° (decomp).

6. C. A. Anirudhan, W. B. Whalley and (in part) Mrs. M. M. E. Badran, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 629.

7. C. A. Anirudhan, D. W. Mathieson and W. B. Whalley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 634.

* All the m.ps. are uncorrected.

8. Helan V. Taylor and Muriel L. Tomlinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2724.

The *oxime* prepared in the usual manner was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 110° (Lit.⁵, m.p. 167–69°). (Found : N, 4.3. C₁₈H₁₇O₄N requires N, 4.5%).

Fischer indole reaction : Chroman-3-one (0.1 g.), phenylhydrazine (1.0 ml.) and acetic acid (2.5 ml.) were heated for two minutes when the *chromenoindole* (VI, R = H) separated. On crystallisation from acetic acid, it was obtained as darkish needles, m.p. 206–08°. (Found : C, 81.1; H, 4.8; N, 6.1. C₁₅H₁₁ON requires C, 81.4; H, 5.0; N, 6.23%).

6-*Methyl-3-cyano-1 : 2 benzopyran* : 4-Methylsalicyl-aldehyde (5.0 g.), acrylonitrile (7.5 ml.) and water (12.5 ml.) were treated very slowly during 48 hr. with sodium hydroxide (7.5 g.) in water (15 ml.), the mixture was gently boiled. After a further 24 hr. the solution was extracted with ether and the ether washed with sodium hydroxide solution and then water. After drying (MgSO₄) and evaporation, 6-*methyl-3-cyano-1 : 2-benzopyran* (1.5 g.) remained. It crystallised from benzene in white leaflets, m.p. 165°. Methylsalicylaldehyde (2.0 g.) was recovered. (Found : C, 77.81; H, 4.87. C₁₁H₈ON requires, C, 77.68; H, 4.7%). The IR spectrum showed absorption at 2240 cm⁻¹ (cyanide).

6-*Methyl-1 : 2-benzopyran-3-carboxylic Acid* : 6-Methyl-3-cyano-1 : 2-benzopyran (1.2 g.) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide (10 ml.; 10%) until evolution of ammonia ceased (about one hr.). Acidification gave the *acid* (800 mg.), m.p. 185–88°. It was crystallised from acetic acid as light brown needles, m.p. 196–98°. (Found : C, 69.25; H, 5.6. C₁₁H₁₀O₃ requires C, 69.47; H, 5.26%).

The *amide* was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from water as shining plates, m.p. 195–96°. (Found : N, 7.32. C₁₁H₁₁O₂N requires, N, 7.4%). The IR spectrum showed absorption at 1650 cm⁻¹ (amide).

6-*Methylchroman-3-one* : The crude carboxylic acid (600 mg.) suspended in dry benzene (1 ml.) was treated with oxalyl chloride (1 ml.) in cold and left overnight when all the acid went into the solution. The excess of oxalyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure and the last traces were removed by the successive addition of dry benzene followed by its removal in vacuum. The residual oily acid chloride (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone (10 ml.) at 0°, and to it was added dropwise a solution of azide (0.26 g.) in water (1.5 ml.) with stirring. After ten minutes ice-water (6.0 ml.) was added when the azide (0.5 g.), m.p. 92–94° (decomp), separated in crystalline form. It was dried up by keeping in a vacuum desiccator. The IR spectrum showed absorption at 2150 cm⁻¹ (azide).

The above azide (0.5 g.) was refluxed with dry ethanol (5 ml.) for 1 hr. when brisk evolution of nitrogen was observed below the boiling point of alcohol. Alcohol was then removed under reduced pressure when 6-*methyl-3-carbethoxyamino-1 : 2 benzopyran* (0.45 g.) was obtained as a thick oil. It was decomposed by refluxing for 1 hr. with sulphuric acid (5 ml.; 15%). It was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (MgSO₄). On evaporation of the solvent, the residual oil distilled at 165–70°/0.7 mm. to give 6-*methylchroman-3-one* (250 mg.) as a colourless oil. (Found : C, 73.99; H, 6.0. C₁₀H₁₀O₂ requires C, 74.07; H, 6.1%). The I.R. spectrum showed absorption at 1790 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ketone).

2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid as yellow needles, m.p. 201–202°. (Found : N, 16.2; $C_{16}H_{14}O_5N_4$ requires N, 16.3%).

The *semicarbazone* prepared in the usual manner was crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 192°. (Found : N, 22.59; $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires, N, 22.73%).

Fisher indole reaction : A mixture of 6-methylchroman-3-one (0.1 g.), phenylhydrazine (1.0 ml.) and acetic acid (2 ml.) was warmed for 5 minutes. On cooling the 2-methylchromenoindole separated. It was crystallised from acetic acid as darkish needles, m.p. 189° (decomp.). (Found : N, 5.87. $C_{16}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 5.95%).

6-Methylchroman-3-one from 3-methyl-6-methoxyphenylacetic Acid : 3-Methyl-6-methoxyphenylacetic acid, m.p. 134° (Lit.⁹, m.p. 131–33°) (0.5 g.) was suspended in dry benzene (1.0 ml.) and treated with oxalyl chloride (1.0 ml.) in cold and left for 2 hr. at room temperature. The excess of the oxalyl chloride was then removed by washing twice with dry benzene when the acid chloride was obtained as a thick brown oil. It was dissolved in dry ether and added slowly to cold ethereal diazomethane (from 5.0 g. of nitrosomethyl urea) and the mixture left overnight. The diazo ketone was obtained as an oil on removal of ether in vacuum at the room temperature. On treatment with boron trifluoride etherate (0.4 ml.) in dry ether (2 ml.), it underwent exothermic decomposition. After keeping for 10 minutes, it was washed thoroughly with water and dried ($MgSO_4$). On evaporation of the solvent and distillation, 6-methylchroman-3-one was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. 165–70°/0.7 mm. and was identified with the product described earlier (2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. and mixed m.p. 201–202°; *semicarbazone*, m.p. and mixed m.p. 191–192°).

Reaction of chroman-3-one with phenylmagnesium bromide : Chroman-3-one (0.37 g.) in dry ether (5 ml.) was added dropwise to an ethereal solution of phenylmagnesium bromide (Mg, 0.12 g.; C_6H_5Br , 0.56 ml.) when a jelly like mass separated at once. The mixture was refluxed on water bath for 6 hr. and then decomposed carefully with dilute acid, washed the ethereal solution with water and dried ($MgSO_4$). On removal of the solvent, an oil was obtained which was chromatographed over alumina in benzene. 3-Hydroxy-3-phenylchroman was obtained as colourless stout needles after crystallisation from methyl alcohol, m.p. 182–84°. (Found : C, 79.05; H, 6.18. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 79.60; H, 6.10%). The IR spectrum showed absorption at 3340 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl).

The *acetate* prepared by sodium acetate-acetic anhydride method, was crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 188–89°. (Found : C, 76.77; H, 6.23. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.12; H, 5.97%). Similarly 3-hydroxy-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl) chroman was obtained as snow white needles, m.p. 224° from *p*-methoxyphenylmagnesium bromide (Mg, 0.23 g.; *p*-bromoanisole, 1.65 g.). (Found : C, 74.98; H, 6.4. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.2%).

Isoflavilyum perchlorate separated as brown wooly needles, m.p. 191–192° (acetic acid) on boiling the alcohol with trityl perchlorate in acetic acid. The analysis could not be done as it exploded during combustion.

Chemical Laboratory,
Patna University,
Patna-5.

Received September 13, 1968.